

A STUDY ON EMPLOYEE SATISFACTION AT APOLLO PHARMACIES LTD**Bhavana R¹, Muthumani S², Bethel Erastus-Obilo³**¹MBA Student, Jerusalem College of Engineering, Chennai, Tamil Nadu, India²Professor And Head MBA, Jerusalem College of Engineering, Chennai, Tamil Nadu, India³Vice President of Academic Affairs & Professor of Criminal Justice, University of Atlanta, Atlanta, GA**Abstract:**

The research project entitled 'A STUDY ON EMPLOYEE SATISFACTION AT APOLLO PHARMACY LTD' is an attempt to understand how effectively technology has improved and holds the strength and weakness. The sample size of the study is 105. The research design carried out of this study is descriptive research. Primary data are collected from the Workers, secondary data are gathered from published by someone else for a different purpose than your current research. The findings of the study were arrived at based on the analysis conducted.

Keywords:

Analysis, Research

INTRODUCTION

The most precious resource in any organisation is thought to be its human resources. It is the culmination of innate aptitudes, learned knowledge, and skill sets embodied in the skills and talents of working people, including managers, executives, and entry-level workers. It should be mentioned that in order to accomplish both individual and organisational goals, human resources should be utilised to the fullest extent possible. Thus, an employee's performance is what ultimately determines whether or not goals are achieved. The phrase "employee satisfaction" refers to whether or not workers are comfortable and happy and getting what they need and want from their jobs. . Numerous metrics assert that motivation, objective achievement, and a positive work environment are all influenced by employee satisfaction. While having happy workers is generally a good thing for your company, it can also be a downer if you have substandard workers who stick around because they like their jobs. The phrase describes a person's whole working relationship with his or her employer, for which they are compensated. The end state is sensation that is accompanied by an impulse of its purpose; satisfaction does not mean the basic feeling state that is present when any goal is attained. This project report mainly focused on a study on employee's satisfaction on APOLLO PHARMACY Ltd. Employee satisfaction is an important factor which will influence the growth and profitability of the firm. Employee satisfaction is terminology used to describe whether employees fulfilling their desire and need at work many measures purport that employee motivation, employees goal achievement and positive employee morale in the work place.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE:

Ekta Sinha2019 ,Findings of this study focused on three factors namely Behavioral, organizational and environmental factors. These factors attempted to find the relation between these factors and employee job satisfaction and it was found that all the three factors have a positive impact on job satisfaction. The study concluded that organizational factors are the most important aspect for job satisfaction of the employees in a company i.e. if the employees are treated equally and fairly and they are properly supervised, their level of satisfaction can be increased towards their job. The research design used in the research was descriptive. This research was used because it is a good structured instrument for collection of data. The research method used was survey method. The research technique used was Questionnaire. In all the above research, Researchers have found that for the growth of any organization employee satisfaction is very important. A few factors that were prominent to the employee satisfaction in the researches before were income, promotion, feeling of fulfillment, work environment, relations with superior. Muhammad Rizwan,Waqas Mehmood Khan2020. Workplace, facets of employees and job discipline are related to working situations. Organization tasks and job activities training, capabilities, utilization, health, secure and working period is deal in it. Employees want relax and ease surroundings and these factors regulate on employee satisfaction. Organization gains employee satisfaction by supplied this environment. Physical job conditions primarily ascribed on low job satisfaction levels.Caterina C. Bulgarella2021.The empirical literature summarized the criticality of the relationship between employee attitudes and customer satisfaction. . Employees can strongly contribute to an organization's success by having a customer-centric approach in their work and in their work-related interactions. However, they are more likely to do so if they are satisfied with their job. Employee satisfaction

is the result of a holistic approach that involves strategic steps such as: Service Climate ,Supportive Management Work Effort, Job Satisfaction, Employee Service Quality.

Dr. L.W Poter2022.While employee satisfaction and employee engagement are both critical to maintaining a happy and productive workforce, achieving satisfaction without engagement will have significantly less impact on business results. After all, engaged employees are emotionally committed to working hard, demonstrating initiative, and expending extra discretionary effort — and doing so in alignment with strategic priorities to move the organization forward. It’s no wonder that employee engagement has been associated with higher workforce productivity and customer satisfaction as well as lower absenteeism and turnover. To start reaping bottom-line benefits that a truly engaged workforce promises, organizations must adopt a more dynamic approach to both satisfaction and engagement that incorporates more frequent measurements — not just a once a-year snapshot to identify trends and create effective change. By taking the satisfaction and engagement pulse of employees periodically throughout the year, HR leaders can develop and implement engagement initiatives and management strategies that take into account not only employees’ present perceptions, but also their past experiences and future expectations. The end result is a more sustained increase in employee engagement that drives competitive success and bottom-line results.

METHODOLOGY

Both primary and secondary data were used in this investigation. Using a questionnaire form, the primary data were gathered from college students and members of the public sector. A questionnaire was used to gather information. A Google form was used to deliver the questionnaire to everyone. The majority of the questionnaire's questions focused on using mobile payment systems. one hundred one respondents were recruited for the present study. Numerous books, journals, research articles, magazines, and websites were the sources of the secondary data. Finding the relationship between the impact of mobile payments and specific references among them is the study's main goal. Understanding use acceptance is one of the secondary goals of the interaction between awareness and mobile payments. To satisfaction of e-payment among student. The total population of 105 respondents was taken in consideration. The respondents were the among all. Efforts were made to include equal number of respondents from each category. Limitations of the study: The result is based only on the sample which is collected using convenient sampling method. A sample size of only 105 respondents was taken in consideration. The findings will differ with larger sample size. were made to include equal number of respondents from each category. The study is focused on use of online payment methods among Jerusalem college students

ANALYSIS

TABLE 1. Gender

GENDER	NO. OF RESPONDENTS	PERCENTAGE
Male	56.7	56.7
Female	43.3	43.3
Total	100	100

INFERENCE: From the above table it is interpreted that 56.7% are male and 43.3% of respondents are female. Majority (56.7%) are male.

2. AGE FOR RESPONDENTS :

TABLE 2.AGE

AGE	NO. OF RESPONDENTS
Below-25	58.7
25-30	22.1
31-40	18
41-50	2
Total	100

INTERPRETATION: From the above table it is interpreted that 58.7 are Below 25 years, 22.1 are 25- 30 years, 17.3 are 31 - 40 years and 1.9 are 41-50 and above. Majority (58.7) are Below 25 years.

3. EDUCATIONAL QUALIFICATION:

TABLE 3.

EDUCATIONAL QUALIFICATION	NO. OF RESPONDENTS
SSLC	4.8
HSC	16.3
UNDERGRADUATE	77.9
POSTGRADUATE	1.0
TOTAL	100

INTERPRETATION: From the above table it is interpreted that 5% are SSLC,17% are HSC,81% are Undergraduate,1% are Postgraduate. Majority are (81%) Undergraduate.

4.DESIGNATION:

TABLE 4:

DESIGNATION	NO. OF RESPONDENTS
Trainee pharmacist	14.4
Pharmacy aide	32.7
Pharmacy trainee	6.7
Senior recruiter	6.7
Junior recruiter	7.7
Recruiter	13.5
HR department	18.3
Total	100

INTERPRETATION: From the above table it is interpreted that 15 % are trainee pharmacist,34% are pharmacy aide,7% are pharmacy trainee,7% are senior recruiter,8% are junior recruiter, 14% are recruiter, 19% are HR department. Majority are (34%) pharmacy aide

5. MONTHLY INCOME:

TABLE 5:

MONTHLY INCOME	NO.OF RESPONDENTS
Greater than 15000	48.1
Lesser than 15000	51.9
Total	100

INTERPRETATION: From the above table it is interpreted that 50% are greater than 150000 and 54% lesser than 150000. Majority are (54%) lesser than 150000.

ANOVA

To identify the factors that motivates the employees.

NULL HYPOTHESIS (H0): There is a significance difference to identify the factors that motivates the employees

ALTERNATIVE HYPOTHESIS (H1): There is no significance to identify the factors that motivates the employees

What is the primary factor that motivates you at work?

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	5.295	3	1.765	2.304	.082
Within Groups	76.618	100	.766		
Total	81.913	103			

INFERENCE: The significant value 0.001 is less than the table significant value ($0.082 < 0.05$).
H0 is rejected and H1 is accepted. Therefore, there is significance difference to identify the factors that motivates the employees.

Correlations

To measure the satisfaction level of the employees.

NULL HYPOTHESIS (H0): There is a significance difference to measure the satisfaction level of the employees.

ALTERNATIVE HYPOTHESIS (H1): There is no significance to measure the satisfaction level of the employees.

	What aspects of your job do you find most fulfilling?	How satisfied are you with your relationship with your immediate supervisor?
What aspects of your job do you find most fulfilling?	Pearson Correlation	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	-.065
		.515

	N	104	104
How satisfied are you with your relationship with your immediate supervisor?	Pearson Correlation	-.065	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.515	
	N	104	104

INFERENCE: The significant value 0.001 is less than the table significant value (0.515<0.05). H0 is rejected and H1 is accepted. Therefore, there is significance difference to measure the satisfaction level of the employees

CHI-SQUARE

To appraise the employees and understand factors which plays an important role in their job satisfaction.
NULL HYPOTHESIS (H0): There is no significance difference of appraise the employees and understand factors which plays an important role in their job satisfaction.

Test Statistics

	How satisfied are you with the level of collaboration within your team in rate scale of 1 to 5?	How long to you get bonus as a part of your performance appraisal ?
Chi-Square	29.212 ^a	5.846 ^a
df	2	2
Asymp. Sig.	.000	.054

a. 0 cells (0.0%) have expected frequencies less than 5. The minimum expected cell frequency is 34.7.

INFERENCE: The significant value 0.000 is less than the table significant value (0.000<0.05). H0 is rejected and H1 is accepted.

Therefore, there is significance difference of various activities involved in the recruitment process.

FINDINGS

From the above table it is interpreted that 56.7% are male and 43.3% of respondents are female. Majority (56.7%) are male. From the above table it is interpreted that 58.7 are Below 25 years, 22.1 are 25- 30 years, 17.3 are 31 - 40 years and 1.9 are 41- 50 and above. Majority (58.7) are Below 25 years. From the above table it is interpreted that 5% are SSLC,17% are HSC,81% are Undergraduate,1% are Postgraduate. Majority are (81%) Undergraduate. From the above table it is interpreted that 15 % are trainee pharmacist,34% are pharmacy aide,7% are pharmacy trainee,7% are senior recruiter,8% are junior recruiter, 14% are recruiter, 19% are HR department. Majority are (34%) pharmacy aide. From the above table it is interpreted that 50% are greater than 150000 and 54% lesser than 150000. Majority are (54%) lesser than 150000.

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SUGGESTION

Provide actionable recommendations for Apollo Pharmacy Ltd to enhance collaborative satisfaction among employees. Offer specific strategies for improving salary and benefits structures to positively impact employee satisfaction and collaboration.

Insights into particular areas that Apollo Pharmacies Ltd. needs to focus on and develop in order to promote a more cooperative and satisfying work environment.

REFERENCE

Ekta Sinha 2019 ,Findings of this study focused on three factors namely Behavioral, organizational and environmental factors.

Manoj Verghese & Dalvinder Singh Wadhwa 2020 Study concluded that the overall employees with special reference to KRIBHCO,found that with respect to experience the satisfaction level of the employees differ significantly regarding salary.

Muhammad Rizwan,Waqas Mehmood Khan 2021. Workplace, facets of employees and job discipline are related to working situations.

Caterina C. Bulgarella 2022.The empirical literature summarized the criticality of the relationship between employee attitudes and customer satisfaction**Dr. L.W Poter2022** .While employee satisfaction and employee engagement are both critical to maintaining a happy and productive workforce, achieving satisfaction without engagement will have significantly less impact on business results.